

MAGNETOELASTIC RESPONSES OF A BI-LAYERED COMPOSITE CYLINDER WITH AN EMBEDDED TIME-HARMONIC EIGENSTRAIN

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1 Introduction

Eigenstrain is a generic name for nonelastic strains such as hygrothermal expansion and misfit strains; the stress caused by the eigenstrain is called eigenstress, accordingly. Eigenstrain problem is significant specifically in media including microstructural imperfection of non-homogeneity or inclusion [1]. Furthermore, subjecting an electrically conducting composite with external magnetic field induces Lorentz force in the medium which changes the magnetoelastic responses of the multifield media [2]. Due to the application of composites in the presence of magnetic field in geophysics and optics, magnetoelastic analysis of composites is of great significance.

There exist a bunch of investigations in the literature on the classical micromechanical problem of eigenstrain in media with inclusion or non-homogeneity. The hygrothermal effects on the fiber composites by simulating the physical problem with a prescribed, constant axial eigenstrain to the fiber material were studied by Takao et al. [3]. Mikata and Nemat-Nasser [4] acquired an exact closed-form solution for the interaction of a harmonic wave with a dynamic inhomogeneity. The time-harmonic elastic field caused by an infinitely long circular cylindrical inclusion was obtained by Cheng and Batra [5]. Pan [6] studied the two-dimensional Eshelby problem in anisotropic piezoelectric biomaterials with uniform eigenstrain and eigenelectric fields. A closed form solution for the elastic field of an elliptical inhomogeneity with a quadratic polynomial eigenstrain using the principle of minimum potential energy was obtained by Guo et al. [7]. Hassan et al. [8] developed a

micromechanical model for smart three-dimensional composite structures reinforced by a periodic grid of generally cylindrical reinforcement which also exhibit the piezoelectric behavior. Akbarzadeh and Chen [9] provided an analytical solution for magnetoelastic analysis of multi-layered and functionally graded (FG) composite cylinders with embedded time-harmonic eigenstrain.

Magnetoelasticity has also attracted much interests among researchers in the field of smart composites. Wang and Ding [10] investigated the radial vibration of a multilayered piezoelectric/magnetostrictive composite hollow sphere with perfectly bonded interfaces. Dai and Wang [11] presented an analytical solution for a piezoelectric hollow cylinder under magnetic, thermal, electrical, and mechanical loading. Dai et al. [12] also obtained an analytical solution for electromagnetoelastic behavior of functionally graded piezoelectric material (FGPM) solid cylinder and sphere subjected to a uniform magnetic field, external pressure, and electric loading. Loghman and Moradi [13] investigated the time-dependent creep responses of a an FGPM sphere subjected to an internal pressure, a uniform temperature rise, and the electromagnetic field. The magneto-electroelastic responses of rotating and radially polarized cylinders induced by different hygrothermal and mechanical boundary conditions were studied by Akbarzadeh and Chen [14].

The present work obtains analytical solutions for magnetoelastic responses of an infinitely-long bi-layered composite cylinder with embedded polynomial eigenstrain in the internal core. Time-

harmonic responses are acquired for the composite cylinder with quadratic polynomial and dynamic eigenstrain and subjected with external magnetic field. The closed form solutions for displacement and stress components are found in terms of Bessel and Struve functions. The effects of magnetic and dynamic eigenstrain on the magnetoelastic are also investigated.

2 Governing Equations:

The governing equations for magnetoelastic responses of a bi-layered infinitely-long composite cylinders with embedded harmonic eigenstrain are given in this section.

Consider an infinitely long bi-layered cylinder subjected to an external constant magnetic field H_z in the cylindrical coordinate (r, θ, z) . The outer radius of the internal and external layer are, respectively, R_1 and R_2 . The internal core experiences an axisymmetric, radially varying, and time-harmonic eigenstrain with angular frequency ω as follows [15]:

$$\mathcal{E}_{jk}^{*(1)}(r, t) = (A_0 + A_1 r + A_2 r^2) \delta_{jk} e^{-i\alpha t} \quad (1)$$

where δ_{jk} ($j, k = 1, 2, 3$) is Kronecker delta, A_l ($l = 0, 1, 2$) are the coefficients for the quadratic polynomial of eigenstrain, and $i = \sqrt{-1}$. Moreover, r and t stand for the radial coordinate and time. The total strain $\mathcal{E}_{ij}^{(k)}$ is considered as the summation of the elastic strain $e_{ij}^{(k)}$ and eigenstrain $\mathcal{E}_{ij}^{*(k)}$:

$$\mathcal{E}_{ij}^{(k)} = e_{ij}^{(k)} + \mathcal{E}_{ij}^{*(k)} \quad (2)$$

in which the superscript $k = 1, 2$ represents for the internal and external layers of composite cylinder. Using Hooke's law, elastic strain is related to stress $\sigma_{ij}^{(k)}$ as follows:

$$\sigma_{ij}^{(k)} = C_{ijmn}^{(k)} e_{mn}^{(k)} = C_{ijmn}^{(k)} (\mathcal{E}_{mn}^{(k)} - \mathcal{E}_{mn}^{*(k)}) \quad (3)$$

where C_{ijkl} ($i, j, k, l = 1, 2, 3$) are elastic moduli. The constitutive equation (3) is simplified for axisymmetric and plane-strain problems as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{rr}^{(1)} &= \frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} ((1-\nu_1)u_{,r}^{(1)} + \nu_1 \frac{u^{(1)}}{r} - (1+\nu_1)(A_0 + A_1 r + A_2 r^2)e^{-i\alpha t}) \\ \sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(1)} &= \frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} (\nu_1 u_{,r}^{(1)} + (1-\nu_1) \frac{u^{(1)}}{r} - (1+\nu_1)(A_0 + A_1 r + A_2 r^2)e^{-i\alpha t}) \\ \sigma_{zz}^{(1)} &= \frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} (\nu_1 u_{,r}^{(1)} + \nu_1 \frac{u^{(1)}}{r} - (1+\nu_1)(A_0 + A_1 r + A_2 r^2)e^{-i\alpha t}) \\ \sigma_{rr}^{(2)} &= \frac{2\mu_2}{1-2\nu_2} ((1-\nu_2)u_{,r}^{(2)} + \nu_2 \frac{u^{(2)}}{r}) \\ \sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(2)} &= \frac{2\mu_2}{1-2\nu_2} (\nu_2 u_{,r}^{(2)} + (1-\nu_2) \frac{u^{(2)}}{r}) \\ \sigma_{zz}^{(2)} &= \frac{2\mu_2 \nu_2}{1-2\nu_2} (u_{,r}^{(2)} + \frac{u^{(2)}}{r}) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The equation of motion for an electrically conducting solid in the presence of Lorentz force is [16]:

$$\sigma_{ij,j}^{(k)} + f_i^{(k)} = \rho^{(k)} u_{i,t}^{(k)} \quad (5)$$

in which $f_i^{(k)}$ and $\rho^{(k)}$ are, respectively, the Lorentz force and density. Eq. (4) can be rewritten for axisymmetric problems as follows [17]:

$$\sigma_{rr,r}^{(k)} + \frac{\sigma_{rr}^{(k)} - \sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(k)}}{r} + \mu'_k H_z^2 (u_{,rr}^{(k)} + \frac{u_{,r}^{(k)}}{r} - \frac{u^{(k)}}{r^2}) = \rho_k u_{tt}^{(k)} \quad (6)$$

where μ'_k represents for the magnetic permeability.

3 Solution Procedures

Due to the harmonic eigenstrain equation (1), displacement could be expressed as:

$$u^{(k)}(r, t) = \bar{u}^{(k)}(r) e^{-i\alpha t} \quad (7)$$

Similar time-harmonic form could be assumed for stress components. Using Eqs. (4) and (6), the following magnetoelastic governing differential equations are obtained for the composite layer:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{u}_{,rr}^{(1)} + \frac{\bar{u}_{,r}^{(1)}}{r} - \left(\frac{1}{r^2} - a_1^2\right)\bar{u}^{(1)} &= b_1^2(A_1 + 2A_2r) \\ \bar{u}_{,rr}^{(2)} + \frac{\bar{u}_{,r}^{(2)}}{r} - \left(\frac{1}{r^2} - a_2^2\right)\bar{u}^{(2)} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned} a_k &= \omega \sqrt{\frac{\rho_k(1-2\nu_k)}{2\mu_k(1-\nu_k) + (1-2\nu_k)\mu'_k H^2}} \quad (k=1,2) \\ b_1 &= \sqrt{\frac{2\mu_1(1+\nu_1)}{2\mu_1(1-\nu_1) + (1-2\nu_1)\mu'_1 H^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The governing differential equations (8) are analytically solved by Bessel and Struve functions. The solutions are expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{u}^{(1)} &= C_1 Y_1(a_1 r) + C_2 J_1(a_1 r) + \\ &\frac{b_1^2}{2a_1^4} (\pi a_1^2 A_1 H_1(a_1 r) + 4a_1^2 A_2 r) \\ \bar{u}^{(2)} &= C_3 J_1(a_2 r) + C_4 Y_1(a_2 r) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

in which C_n ($n=1,2,3,4$) is the integration constants and J_1 and Y_1 are first-order Bessel functions of the first and second kind; H_1 is Struve H function of the first-order. The Struve function $H_\nu(r)$ may be defined in the following power series [18]:

$$H_\nu(r) = \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{\nu+1} \sum_{p=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^p}{\Gamma(p+\frac{3}{2})\Gamma(p+\nu+\frac{3}{2})} \left(\frac{r}{2}\right)^{2p} \quad (11)$$

where Γ stands for Gamma function and ν is the order of Struve function.

To accomplish the solution procedure, the integration constants in Eq. (10) should be determined by satisfying boundary conditions. The boundary conditions for the perfectly bonded composite cylinder is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{u}^{(1)}(r=0) &\text{ is finite} \\ \bar{u}^{(2)}(r=R_1) &= \bar{u}^{(1)}(r=R_1) \\ \bar{\sigma}_{rr}^{(1)}(r=R_1) &= \bar{\sigma}_{rr}^{(2)}(r=R_1) \\ \bar{\sigma}_{rr}^{(2)}(r=R_2) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

in which $\bar{\sigma}_{rr}$ is defined in the same form of \bar{u} in Eq. (7). Due to the singularity of the Bessel function of the second kind at $r=0$, the first boundary condition of Eq. (12) results in $C_1=0$. The other three boundary conditions lead to the algebraic

equation for determining the integration constants as follows:

$$K_{ij} C_j = F_i \quad (i, j = 2, 3, 4) \quad (13)$$

The components of K_{ij} and F_i have been specified in Appendix. The stress components are obtained by employing Eqs. (4) and (10). The radial stresses for the internal and external layers are:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}_{rr}^{(1)} &= \frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} [a_1(1-\nu_1)(J_0(a_1 r) - \frac{J_1(a_1 r)}{a_1 r}) + \\ &\frac{\nu_1}{r} J_1(a_1 r)] C_2 - \frac{2\mu_1(1+\nu_1)}{1-2\nu_1} A_0 + \\ &\frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} [-(1+\nu_1)r + \frac{b_1^2 \nu_1 \pi H_1(a_1 r)}{2a_1^2 r}] + \\ &\frac{b_1^2(1-\nu_1)\pi}{4a_1} \left(\frac{a_1 r}{2\sqrt{\pi}\Gamma(\frac{5}{2})} + H_0(a_1 r) - H_2(a_1 r)\right) A_1 + \\ &\frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} [-(1+\nu_1)r^2 + \frac{2b_1^2}{a_1^2}] A_2 \\ \bar{\sigma}_{rr}^{(2)} &= \frac{2\mu_2}{1-2\nu_2} [a_2(1-\nu_2)(J_0(a_2 r) - \frac{J_1(a_2 r)}{a_2 r}) \\ &+ \frac{\nu_2}{r} J_1(a_2 r)] C_3 + \frac{2\mu_2}{1-2\nu_2} [a_2(1-\nu_2)(Y_0(a_2 r) \\ &- \frac{Y_1(a_2 r)}{a_2 r}) + \frac{\nu_2}{r} Y_1(a_2 r)] C_4 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The hoop and axial stresses components are respectively given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}_{\theta\theta}^{(1)} &= \frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} [a_1 \nu_1 (J_0(a_1 r) - \frac{J_1(a_1 r)}{a_1 r}) + \\ &\frac{1-\nu_1}{r} J_1(a_1 r)] C_2 - \frac{2\mu_1(1+\nu_1)}{1-2\nu_1} A_0 + \\ &\frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} [-(1+\nu_1)r + \frac{b_1^2(1-\nu_1)\pi H_1(a_1 r)}{2a_1^2 r}] + \\ &\frac{b_1^2 \nu_1 \pi}{4a_1} \left(\frac{a_1 r}{2\sqrt{\pi}\Gamma(\frac{5}{2})} + H_0(a_1 r) - H_2(a_1 r)\right) A_1 + \\ &\frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} [-(1+\nu_1)r^2 + \frac{2b_1^2}{a_1^2}] A_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{\theta\theta}^{(2)} = \frac{2\mu_2}{1-2\nu_2} [a_2\nu_2(J_0(a_2r) - \frac{J_1(a_2r)}{a_2r}) + \frac{1-\nu_2}{r} J_1(a_2r)]C_3 + \frac{2\mu_2}{1-2\nu_2} [a_2\nu_2(Y_0(a_2r) - \frac{Y_1(a_2r)}{a_2r}) + \frac{1-\nu_2}{r} Y_1(a_2r)]C_4 \quad (15)$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{zz}^{(1)} = \frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} [a_1\nu_1(J_0(a_1r) - \frac{J_1(a_1r)}{a_1r}) + \frac{\nu_1}{r} J_1(a_1r)]C_2 - \frac{2\mu_1(1+\nu_1)}{1-2\nu_1} A_0 + \frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} [-(1+\nu_1)r + \frac{b_1^2\nu_1\pi H_1(a_1r)}{2a_1^2r}] + \frac{b_1^2\nu_1\pi}{4a_1} (\frac{a_1r}{2\sqrt{\pi}\Gamma(\frac{5}{2})} + H_0(a_1r) - H_2(a_1r)]A_1 + \frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} [-(1+\nu_1)r^2 + \frac{4b_1^2\nu_1}{a_1^2}]A_2$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_{zz}^{(2)} = \frac{2\mu_2\nu_2}{1-2\nu_2} [a_2(J_0(a_2r) - \frac{J_1(a_2r)}{a_2r}) + \frac{J_1(a_2r)}{r}]C_3 + \frac{2\mu_2\nu_2}{1-2\nu_2} [a_2(Y_0(a_2r) - \frac{Y_1(a_2r)}{a_2r}) + \frac{Y_1(a_2r)}{r}]C_4 \quad (16)$$

4 Results and Discussion

The numerical results are presented in this section for magnetoelastic responses of bi-layered composite infinitely-long cylinders with embedded time-harmonic and quadratic polynomial eigenstrain. The influence of external magnetic field, angular frequency, and polynomial eigenstrain on the radial displacement, radial stress, hoop stress, and axial stress distribution is investigated.

The inner layer of composite cylinder is assumed to be Steel, while the outer layer could be Steel or Aluminum. The material properties of layers could be found in Table 1. The magnetic permeability of two layers are assumed to be the same. The coefficients of eigenstrain polynomial are also taken to be unity $A_l (l=0,1,2)=1$ in order to focus on

the effect of eigenstrain distribution on the magnetoelastic responses.

Table 1 Material properties [19]

Steel	Aluminum Alloys
$E = 200 \times 10^9 \text{ Pa}$	$E = 70 \times 10^9 \text{ Pa}$
$\nu = 0.29$	$\nu = 0.33$
$\rho = 7.85 \times 10^3 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$	$\rho = 2.71 \times 10^3 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$

The displacement, stress components, and radial coordinate are depicted in the non-dimensional form as follows:

$$U = \frac{\bar{u}}{R_1 \epsilon_{avg}^*}, \Sigma_{rr} = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{rr}(r)}{\mu_1 \epsilon_{avg}^*}, \Sigma_{\theta\theta} = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{\theta\theta}(r)}{\mu_1 \epsilon_{avg}^*}$$

$$\Sigma_{zz} = \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{zz}(r)}{\mu_1 \epsilon_{avg}^*}, \zeta = \frac{r}{R_1} \quad (23)$$

Figure 1 depicts the effect of uniform non-dimensional external magnetic field $\alpha = \frac{\mu_1' H^2}{E_1}$ on

the displacement and stress distributions of the bi-layered composite cylinder subjected to harmonic eigenstrain with angular frequency $\omega = 1000 \text{ (rad/s)}$. The outer radius of the internal and external layer are assumed to be $R_1 = 1$ and $R_2 = 4$. The inner and outer layers of composite are composed, respectively, of Steel and Aluminum. As shown in Fig.1a, increasing the magnetic field enhances the radial displacement. Similarly, increasing the magnetic field increases the radial, hoop, and axial stresses on the axis of the cylinder, as seen in Figs. 1b through 1d.

Fig. 1. Effect of external magnetic field on: (a) radial displacement, (b) radial stress, (c) hoop stress, and (d) axial stress distribution

The effect of angular frequency ω of the embedded harmonic eigenstrain on the magnetoelastic behavior of composite cylinder with $R_1 = 1$ and $R_2 = 2$ are depicted in Fig. 2. The cylinder is exposed to the uniform magnetic field $\alpha = 1$. In this figure, $\omega = 0$ represents the static eigenstrain.

It is assumed that the internal layer undergoes a quadratic polynomial eigenstrain. Although lower values of angular frequencies do not disturb the magnetoelastic responses significantly, increasing the angular frequency enhances the radial

displacement and tensile radial stress, hoop stress, and axial stress throughout the cylinder.

Fig. 2. Effect of angular frequency on: (a) radial displacement, (b) radial stress, (c) hoop stress, and (d) axial stress distribution

The effect of eigenstrain distribution on the magnetoelastic responses are shown in Fig. 3 for a bi-layered composite cylinder with an embedded time-harmonic eigenstrain $\omega = 1000$ (rad/s) and subjected to a constant magnetic field $\alpha = 1$. The bi-layered cylinder is assumed to be constructed of the same material which is Steel. As seen in Figs. 3a through 3d, the radial displacement and radial stresses are continuous on the interface of the layers; however, the hoop and axial stresses are discontinuous due to the existence of eigenstrain. Higher orders of the polynomial eigenstrain lead to higher radial displacement and compressive radial stresses on the interface of the two layers, as depicted in Figs. 3a and 3b. Furthermore, the eigenstrain distribution of eigenstrain change the hoop stress distribution throughout the cylinder; nonetheless, the effect of polynomial eigenstrain on axial stress distribution through the outer layer is not considerable.

Fig. 3. Effect of polynomial eigenstrain on: (a) radial displacement, (b) radial stress, (c) hoop stress, and (d) axial stress distribution

5 Conclusions

A closed form solution is sought in this paper for the time-harmonic eigenstrain problem in a magnetoelastic bi-layered cylinder with plane strain condition. The eigenstrain distribution is assumed to be of quadratic polynomial. Using Bessel and Struve functions, analytical solutions are found for radial displacement and stress components. As results reveal, the presence of external magnetic field has significant effect on the magnetoelastic response specially on the internal layer with eigenstrain distribution. Furthermore, the angular frequency of eigenstrain and the distribution of the eigenstrain could disturb the structural magnetoelastic responses, remarkably.

Appendix

The components of K_{ij} and F_i in Eq. (13) are given as follows:

$$K_{22} = J_1(a_1 R_1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
K_{23} &= \frac{2\mu_2\chi_1}{1-2\nu_2} [(1-\nu_1)a_2(J_0(a_2R_1) - \frac{J_1(a_2R_1)}{a_2R_1}) \\
&+ \frac{\nu_2J_1(a_2R_1)}{R_1}] - J_1(a_2R_1) \\
K_{24} &= \frac{2\mu_2\chi_1}{1-2\nu_2} [(1-\nu_1)a_2(Y_0(a_2R_1) - \frac{Y_1(a_2R_1)}{a_2R_1}) \\
&+ \frac{\nu_2Y_1(a_2R_1)}{R_1}] - Y_1(a_2R_1) \\
K_{32} &= \frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} ((1-\nu_1)a_1J_0(a_1R_1) + \frac{2\nu_1-1}{R_1} J_1(a_1R_1)) \\
K_{33} &= -\frac{2\mu_2}{1-2\nu_2} ((1-\nu_2)a_2J_0(a_2R_1) + \frac{2\nu_2-1}{R_1} J_1(a_2R_1)) \\
K_{34} &= -\frac{2\mu_2}{1-2\nu_2} ((1-\nu_2)a_2Y_0(a_2R_1) + \frac{2\nu_2-1}{R_1} Y_1(a_2R_1)) \\
K_{42} &= 0 \\
K_{43} &= (1-\nu_2)a_2J_0(a_2R_2) + \frac{2\nu_2-1}{R_2} J_1(a_2R_2) \\
K_{44} &= (1-\nu_2)a_2Y_0(a_2R_2) + \frac{2\nu_2-1}{R_2} Y_1(a_2R_2)
\end{aligned} \tag{A.1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F_2 &= -\frac{b_1^2}{2a_1^4} (\pi a_1^2 H_1(a_1R_1) A_1 + 4R_1 a_1^2 A_2 + 6s_{3,1}(a_1R_1)) \\
F_3 &= \frac{2\mu_1(1+\nu_1)}{1-2\nu_1} A_0 \\
&- \frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} [-(1+\nu_1)R_1 + \frac{b_1^2\nu_1\pi H_1(a_1R_1)}{2a_1^2R_1}] + \\
&\left[\frac{(1-\nu_1)b_1^2\pi}{4a_1} \left(\frac{a_1R_1}{2\sqrt{\pi}\Gamma(\frac{5}{2})} + H_0(a_1R_1) - H_2(a_1R_1) \right) \right] A_1 \\
&- \frac{2\mu_1}{1-2\nu_1} \left[-(1+\nu_1)R_1^2 + \frac{2b_1^2\nu_1}{a_1^2} + \frac{2(1-\nu_1)b_1^2}{a_1^2} \right] A_2 \\
F_4 &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{A.2}$$

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